

Challenges of anonymizing or simulating sensitive time-to-event data on HIV-positive adolescents' sexual behavior

Introduction

For the vignette “When retrospective data is censored data” (Smekens, 2022), I used data from a previous study by Bakeera-Kitaka et al. (2019) which features a survival analysis on survey data of 582 Kenyan and Ugandan adolescents living with HIV on a variety of subjects, including sexual behavior. A large part of the vignette focuses on the operations one needs to perform on the data to get it into the correct format for conducting a survival analysis, with R code included. To make the vignette as useful as it can be, it would be idea to distribute the data alongside it, so that the reader can load the data into R and follow along, executing the commands as they go.

Unfortunately, sharing the data publicly in this case is very difficult due to the highly sensitive nature of the data. Not only is the participant's mere presence in the dataset highly confidential as it signifies HIV positivity, the participants were also minors (between 13 and 17 years old) and the survey included questions on whether the participants had ever had sex, and if so, at what age. There are therefore several overlapping reasons for why the data must be treated extremely confidentially.

Below is a list of variables used in the vignette. There were no direct identifiers (such as name or home address), but several indirect identifiers needed to be used. Other variables, such as scores constructed from questionnaire items that constitute a psychometric scale, can in all likelihood be considered non-identifying.

Table 1: Variables used in the vignette

Variable name	Description	Identifier?
age	Current age	Yes
eversex	Has ever had sex?	Yes
agefirstsex	Age of first sexual intercourse	Yes
ageHIV	Discovered being HIV-infected at what age?	Yes
sex	Male or female	Yes
ARV	Undergoing antiretroviral treatment for HIV?	Yes
stud	Currently in school?	Yes
country	Respondent's country (Uganda or Kenya)	Yes
health	Subjective health, on a scale from 1 to 5	No
at6new_2cat	Psychometric scale measuring own sexual norms	No
fr1_2cat	Psychometric scale measuring peers' sexual norms	No
tscat	Psychometric scale measuring ability to talk about HIV	No

A few approaches were tried to prepare the data so that it could be made publicly available after all.

Anonymization

Anonymizing the dataset would entail modifying it until it no longer identifies any specific participants. One possible criterion for assessing whether a dataset has been sufficiently anonymized

is k-anonymity (Sweeney, 2002), which specifies that each record in the dataset must be identical to at least a given number of other records, so that none can be specifically identified. The required number of other such records is given as $k - 1$. Thus, under $k = 3$, the dataset must consist of groups of no less than three participants each whose identifying variables have the same values. Choosing k is not straightforward, but 3 was chosen as a possible bare minimum for this data.

The open source software Amnesia (<https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>) can be used to assess a dataset's k-anonymity for a given k , and supports certain operations on the dataset to achieve this k-anonymity if it has not been met. For this run, I loaded only those identifying variables into the program which were truly central to the message of the vignette and could not be missed: respondents' current age, whether they had had sex, age of first intercourse, age at which they discovered being infected with HIV, their sex, and whether they were under ARV treatment at the time of the survey.

What type is your data? Toggle All

Choose the columns and their types.

age <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	eversex <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	agefirstsex <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ageHIV <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sex <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ARV <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
int	string	int	int	string	string

The software then requests the user to specify k .

Check if dataset is Anonymous ×

Choose attributes :

- age
- eversex
- agefirstsex
- ageHIV
- sex
- ARV

Choose K :

Next, the software shows whether k-anonymity has been met. In this case, 36% of the observations are problematic, in that they are too unique, not identical to enough other observations. The software then allows to perform one of the two techniques it supports, **data suppression**, which simply removes this problematic 36% so that k-anonymity is achieved.

Check if dataset is Anonymous

"age,eversex,agefirstsex,ageHIV,sex,ARV" is anonymous for $k : 1$.

Percentage of displayed dataset is : 100%

To produce a $k = 3$ suppress 36.21%

36% is not a terrible sacrifice at first glance; perhaps a large reduction in statistical power, but the vignette does not need to have the same conclusiveness as the original paper to make its points. Here, unfortunately, the data suppression removes nearly all participants which had had sex, leaving only 17. The reason for this is likely that these participants have an age of first intercourse which can additionally identify them, whereas the others had a placeholder value of -1 for this variable.

Table 2: Participant numbers before and after data suppression

	Ever had sex?	
	Yes	No
Before anonymization	123	457
After anonymization	17	353

This makes the suppressed dataset quite useless for the vignette, as without so few events, it is difficult to do a meaningful survival analysis. The other technique supported by the Amnesia software is **data generalization** (labeled "hierarchies" in the software), which effectively means categorizing certain variables so that many observations end up in the same category and are therefore no longer identifiable. Again, this would make the dataset near useless for the purposes of the vignette; if age of first intercourse is categorized, then there would only be a small number of possible event times in the survival analysis, and most times would be tied. There would be very little room to find associations between the time to the event and any independent variables.

Figure 1: Kaplan-Meier survival curves by gender, from the published article (Sabrina-Kitaka et al., 2019) and if age were to be categorized into ranges of 5 years.

Other methods exist which are not supported by the Amnesia program; for instance, one could add random noise to the event times to shift them from their true values in a random direction, or add additional observations which are fake and serve to hide the actual participants' data. Many of these techniques are implemented in the R package **sdcmicro** (Templ et al., 2015), but as the main help file states: "...the user should have a detailed knowledge about [Statistical Disclosure Control] when applying the methods on data" (see e.g. Templ, 2017). Given the required time investment, and the possibility that it might still not be acceptable to publish the data at the end of the process, other options were considered instead.

Simulation

Many R packages are available which generate fictitious data under various constraints defined by the user. If a dataset were to be generated by such a program and still be useful for the vignette, then it would be no problem at all to distribute since it doesn't contain any actual participant data.

The R package **faux** (DeBruine, 2023) accepts a dataset, calculates the means, standard deviations and correlations between all the variables and then outputs a new dataset which reproduces the aforementioned statistics but is otherwise not based on the real data at all.

Here is an example command with a few lines of output:

```
sim_df(dat[,c("age", "country", "ARV", "agefirstsex", "ageHIV")], n = 580)
```

Table 3: Data generated by the *faux* package

age	country	ARV	agefirstsex	ageHIV
13,1	1,8	2,6	16,8	12,0
15,9	1,1	1,1	4,4	4,5
15,7	2,0	0,2	-3,2	8,3
13,2	1,7	1,3	0,3	10,7
12,4	0,5	0,9	-12,9	7,5

But herein lies the limitation of the package. As of yet, it generates every variable along a continuous normal distribution, even when they ought to be categorical. But moreover, there is no constraint to make sure that the age of first intercourse is earlier than the current age; they can even be negative.

If the analysis were performed using linear regression, then this approach would still be quite useful, but in the vignette where these variables need to be processed for use in survival analysis, most of the generated records will likely be nonsensical.

To more meaningfully simulate the outcome variable for survival analysis, there is the R package **simsurv** (Brilleman et al., 2021). Generating an outcome variable with this package requires a dataset with values for the independent variables, as well as two other sets of inputs: hazard ratios (on the log scale) as associations with independent variables to simulate, and a functional form for the baseline survivor function, with the parameters it requires.

The output of a cox regression can be used to find suitable hazard ratios, but not for the baseline survivor function, as cox regression avoids modeling this entirely. Instead, a parametric survival regression model must be run, which requires choosing a functional form for the survivor function. There are multiple such functional forms, such as the exponential distribution which models hazard as being constant over time, and the Weibull distribution, which allows hazard to either increase or decrease over time (but not a mixture of the two). Here, a Weibull distribution was chosen.

To verify whether the Weibull distribution is appropriate for this data, the **flexsurv** package (Jackson, 2016) was used. This package has a `flexsurvspline` function which fits a parametric regression model with a given number of splines (that is, “knots” or angles in the survivor function), specified with the parameter k . If $k = 0$, then there are no splines and the function simply models a Weibull distribution. Then, the package can output plots comparing the fitted against the observed survivor function to check whether the fitted form is appropriate. For this data, this was done for boys and girls separately as they were also given separate models in the original paper.

```
mod1 <- flexsurvspline(Surv(surv_time, surv_event) ~ 1,
                       data = dat, subset= sex == 1, k = 0)
plot(mod1)
mod2 <- flexsurvspline(Surv(surv_time, surv_event) ~ 1,
                       data = dat, subset= sex == 2, k = 0)
plot(mod2)
```

Figure 2: Fitted Weibull versus observed survival curves for boys (left) and girls (right)

The fitted curve in red follows the observed survival curve quite well in both cases. Next, the parameters for the Weibull distribution can be taken from the model and plugged into the **simsurv** package, along with log hazard ratios obtained from cox regression and independent variables that were simulated using **faux**. This example is for boys.

```
simsurv(dist="weibull", lambdas=0.2663277, gammas=3.078051, betas=c(
```

```

age=0.2969,
country=1.5369,
ageHIV=0.04019,
ARV=0.5971,
), x=sim_dat_m)

```

The output of this function is a “time” column and an “event” column, as required for survival analysis:

Table 4: Example simsurv output for boys

Time to event or censoring	Event (1) or censored (0)
0,24	1
0,12	1
0,12	1
0,15	1
0,20	1

However, the simulated event times were all unrealistically early. Perhaps this could have been improved by tuning the simulation. Another complication is that the “AgeHIV” variable (at which age the participant became aware of their HIV infection) was modeled as a time-varying covariate in the original paper, but this would require defining a custom hazard function in `simsurv`, so it was incorrectly modeled as a continuous variable in this example. Lastly, even if good data were to be obtained, it would then have had to be converted backwards through all the data management steps shown in the vignette, in order to then show how to convert everything back into the format needed for survival analysis.

All things combined, the time investment proved too great, so the possibility of simulation was dropped as well, and the vignette is distributed without any accompanying data.

Conclusion

Anonymization and simulation are powerful tools that can be used to prepare otherwise sensitive data to be publicly distributed without breaching the confidentiality of the research participants. Although the resulting data may no longer be useful for gaining scientific insights, here we only require them to be didactically useful; the variables must simply be appropriate in nature for conducting survival analysis, and should have similar associations between them as in the original data so that the overall conclusions remain intact.

The tools used in this report go some way towards facilitating these goals, at least for certain kinds of analyses such as linear regression. For survival analysis, however, several difficulties were encountered. Anonymizing a survival dataset via suppression may remove the vast majority of records, as times to event or censoring are often unique, depending on the study design. Data generalization is also unlikely to be an option, as categorizing event times will replace most differences in outcomes with a preponderance of ties, and remove most of the potential of the survival analysis. Lastly, although the `simsurv` package offers an impressively advanced method of simulating the time and event columns which constitute the outcome variable in a survival analysis, it is not straightforward to use, and must itself be given a dataset of independent variables; and if

these independent variables are sensitive, they may have to be simulated as well, perhaps with tools that were not created with survival analysis in mind.

The challenges encountered in this report illustrate that anonymizing sensitive data used in a survival analysis poses certain difficulties that would not have manifested if other techniques had been used. At the same time, the vignette shows that survival analysis is indeed required when analyzing life course events which not every participant may have experienced by a certain age, including sexual behavior. We should work towards establishing a viable workflow for either anonymizing or simulating this kind of data when there is a benefit to making it publicly available.

References

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